

PATH ANALYTICS OF TEACHERS' PSYCHO-DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES AND CLASSROOM INCIVILITY AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN OGUN STATE, NIGERIA*

Rasheed Ayodele KESHINRO¹

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.21058577

Abstract

Classroom incivility remains a persistent threat to effective teaching and learning in secondary schools, particularly in developing educational systems. This study investigated the path analytic relationships between teachers' psycho-demographic variables and classroom incivility among secondary school students in Ogun State, Nigeria.

Anchored in Social Exchange Theory, the study adopted a survey research design and utilised structural equation modelling to examine direct, indirect, and total causal effects of teachers' gender, work experience, academic qualification, teaching efficacy, communicative behaviour, credibility, personality, classroom management, and emotional intelligence on classroom incivility. Participants comprised 450 teachers and 400 senior secondary school students selected through multi-stage sampling procedures.

Findings revealed that teachers' communicative behaviour, credibility, teaching efficacy, emotional intelligence, and work experience exerted significant negative effects on classroom incivility, while gender showed no significant influence. The validated path model demonstrated improved goodness-of-fit indices and accounted for a substantial proportion of variance in students' uncivil behaviours. The study concludes that classroom incivility is largely shaped by teacher-related psycho-demographic factors and recommends targeted teacher training, emotional intelligence development, and evidence-based classroom management policies.

Key words: *Classroom incivility, Teaching efficacy, Communicative behaviour, Credibility, Emotional intelligence.*

1. Introduction

Educational institutions are established to inculcate discipline, civic responsibility, and socially acceptable behaviour among learners. However,

*This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited. Authors retain the copyright of this article.

¹PhD, Department of Counseling and Human Development Studies University of Ibadan, Nigeria, e-mail address: keshinrorasheed123@gmail.com, ORCID iD: <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-1045-6936>

increasing incidents of classroom incivility, ranging from inattentiveness and disrespect to overt aggression have become a major concern in secondary schools. Classroom incivility disrupts instructional flow, erodes teacher authority, and negatively affects students' academic engagement and psychosocial development. Any communicative behaviour, whether verbal or nonverbal, that is frequently displayed by a student or group of students and that has the potential to disrupt the teaching-learning process is considered classroom rudeness (Ogunwole, 2020).

Recent global studies describe classroom incivility as a low-intensity antisocial behaviour with ambiguous intent to harm but with far-reaching educational consequences (Chirag, 2020; Natalie, Elizabeth, Naomi, Anthony, 2025). In Nigeria, reports of student hooliganism, verbal abuse of teachers, and disregard for classroom norms have escalated, prompting policy interventions and public concern. Despite these realities, most empirical investigations have focused on student-based or family-related causes, with limited attention to teacher-based psycho-demographic determinants. Teachers occupy a central position in the classroom social system. Their communication patterns, emotional regulation, credibility, professional competence, and personality traits shape classroom climate and influence students' behavioural responses. Understanding how these teacher variables interact to predict classroom incivility is essential for developing sustainable interventions.

2. Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to examine the path analytic relationships between teachers' psycho-demographic variables and classroom incivility among secondary school students in Ogun State, Nigeria.

Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the relationships among teachers' psycho-demographic variables and classroom incivility.
2. Examine the direct, indirect, and total causal effects of teachers' psycho-demographic variables on classroom incivility.
3. Test the goodness-of-fit of the hypothesised and validated path models.

3. Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance:

1. Teachers' psycho-demographic variables will not significantly predict classroom incivility among secondary school students.
2. There will be no significant direct or indirect effects of teachers' psycho-demographic variables on classroom incivility.
3. The hypothesised path model will not provide a good fit for explaining classroom incivility.

4. Theoretical Framework

The study was anchored on Social Exchange Theory formulated by Homans (1958), which posits that social behaviour results from an exchange process in which

individuals seek to maximise rewards and minimise costs. In classroom settings, students evaluate teachers' behaviours such as fairness, competence, emotional responsiveness, and respect, and respond accordingly. Positive teacher–student relationships and effective classroom management promote cooperation and appropriate classroom conduct (Pianta, 1999).

Similarly, teachers who demonstrate credibility, effective communication, and emotional intelligence tend to encourage students' compliance and civility (McCroskey & Teven, 1999). Conversely, teachers perceived as ineffective or emotionally detached may unintentionally provoke resistance and classroom incivility. Therefore, Social Exchange Theory provides an appropriate framework for explaining how teacher characteristics influence students' classroom behaviour patterns.

5. Empirical Review

Empirical evidence consistently links classroom incivility with negative educational outcomes, including reduced academic engagement, emotional exhaustion, and teacher burnout (Cahyadi, Hendryadi & Mappadang, 2021). Studies have shown that teachers' communicative behaviour significantly predicts classroom orderliness, with clarity and immediacy reducing disruptive conduct (Adewale, Tahir, Ashiru & Sanni, 2025). Teacher credibility has been associated with students' respect, motivation, and compliance (García, Froment & Bohórquez, 2023), while emotional intelligence has been linked to effective classroom control and conflict resolution (Agokei, 2021). Work experience and academic qualification have yielded mixed findings, with some studies reporting positive effects on discipline and others suggesting diminishing returns over time. Notably, existing studies have largely examined these variables in isolation. Few have employed path analytic approaches capable of revealing the complex causal mechanisms through which teacher variables jointly influence classroom incivility. This study addresses that gap.

6. Methodology

6.1. Design

The study adopted a quantitative research design with a cross-sectional approach. Structural equation modelling was employed to test hypothesised causal relationships among variables.

6.2. Population

The population comprised all public secondary school teachers and senior secondary school students in Ogun State, Nigeria.

6.3. Sample and Sampling Procedure

A multi-stage sampling procedure was used. Three senatorial districts were identified, from which nine local government areas were randomly selected. Twenty-seven secondary schools were selected, yielding a sample of 450 teachers and 400 senior secondary school students.

7. Instrumentation

Data for this study were collected using standardised and adapted instruments with established theoretical grounding and psychometric validity. All instruments

were selected based on their relevance to educational settings and prior empirical use. Minor adaptations were made to suit the Nigerian secondary school context, without altering the core constructs measured. Reliability coefficients obtained in the present study confirmed the internal consistency of the instruments.

7.1. Classroom Incivility Scale

Classroom incivility was measured using the Classroom Incivility Scale developed by McKinne (2008). The scale was specifically designed to assess uncivil behaviours in classroom environments, including disrespectful communication, disruptive actions, inattentiveness, and violations of classroom norms. McKinne conceptualised classroom incivility as low-intensity deviant behaviour that disrupts teaching–learning processes without necessarily involving overt aggression. The scale has been widely cited in educational research for its contextual relevance and sensitivity to classroom-based behavioural dynamics. Its use in the present study was considered appropriate because it directly captures student behaviours that undermine instructional effectiveness. The adapted version of the scale yielded a Cronbach’s alpha reliability coefficient of 0.74, indicating acceptable internal consistency.

7.2. Teaching Efficacy Scale

Teachers’ teaching efficacy was assessed using the Teachers’ Sense of Efficacy Scale (TSES) developed by Tschannen-Moran and Hoy (2001). The TSES is grounded in Bandura’s self-efficacy theory and measures teachers’ beliefs about their ability to engage students, manage classrooms, and implement effective instructional strategies. The scale has been extensively validated across cultures and educational levels and is regarded as one of the most robust measures of teacher efficacy. Its inclusion in this study was justified by evidence linking teacher efficacy to classroom control, student engagement, and behavioural outcomes. The reliability coefficient obtained in this study was 0.89, reflecting high internal consistency.

7.3. Teachers’ Communicative Behaviour Scale

Teachers’ communicative behaviour was measured using an adapted version of the Teacher Communication Behaviour Questionnaire developed by McCroskey and Richmond (1996). The instrument assesses dimensions such as clarity, immediacy, feedback, and responsiveness in instructional communication. The scale has been widely applied in classroom-based research and has demonstrated strong predictive validity for student motivation and discipline. In the present study, the instrument yielded a Cronbach’s alpha coefficient of 0.78.

7.4. Teacher Credibility Scale

Teacher credibility was assessed using the Source Credibility Scale developed by McCroskey and Teven (1999). The scale measures students’ perceptions of teachers’ competence, trustworthiness, and goodwill dimensions that are central to effective classroom authority and influence. Prior studies have established that teacher credibility significantly predicts student compliance, respect, and classroom order. The scale was therefore considered particularly relevant for examining classroom incivility. The reliability coefficient obtained in this study was 0.80, indicating satisfactory internal consistency.

7.5. Emotional Intelligence Scale

Teachers' emotional intelligence was measured using the Wong and Law Emotional Intelligence Scale (WLEIS) developed by Law and Wong (2002). The WLEIS is an ability-based self-report instrument that measures four dimensions: self-emotional appraisal, others' emotional appraisal, use of emotion, and regulation of emotion. The scale has been widely employed in organisational and educational research due to its strong construct validity and cross-cultural applicability. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient obtained was 0.78.

7.6. Classroom Management Scale

Classroom management skills were assessed using the Classroom Management Scale developed by Yeliz (2016). The scale measures teachers' ability to organise instructional activities, maintain discipline, manage student behaviour, and create a supportive learning environment. Yeliz's scale was specifically designed for educational contexts and has demonstrated strong validity in assessing teachers' managerial competence. Its use in the present study was appropriate given the central role of classroom management in preventing disruptive and uncivil behaviours. The reliability coefficient obtained in this study was 0.77.

7.7. Personality Inventory

Teachers' personality traits were measured using the Ten-Item Personality Inventory (TIPI) developed by Gosling, Rentfrow, and Swann (2003). The TIPI is a brief measure of the Big Five personality dimensions- openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and emotional stability. Although concise, the TIPI has been shown to possess adequate convergent validity with longer personality inventories and is particularly suitable for large-scale surveys where questionnaire length is a concern. Its inclusion in this study was justified by evidence linking personality traits to classroom interaction styles and behavioural regulation. The adapted instrument yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.71.

8. Method of Data Analysis

Data collected were coded and analysed using inferential statistical techniques. Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) was employed to examine the causal relationships among teachers' psycho-demographic variables and classroom incivility.

Specifically, path analysis, a subset of SEM, was used to test the hypothesised causal model linking teachers' gender, work experience, academic qualification, teaching efficacy, communicative behaviour, credibility, personality, classroom management, and emotional intelligence to classroom incivility. Standardised regression weights (β coefficients) were computed to determine the magnitude and direction of relationships among variables. The analysis proceeded in two stages. First, the hypothesised path model was tested to examine the initial pattern of relationships among variables. Second, a validated (trimmed) model was developed by removing non-significant paths in line with theoretical justification and modification indices. This process enhanced model parsimony and explanatory power. Model adequacy was assessed using multiple goodness-of-fit indices, including the Chi-square (χ^2) statistic, Comparative Fit Index (CFI), and Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA). The validated model was considered to

have an acceptable fit where CFI values approached or exceeded 0.90 and RMSEA values were less than or equal to 0.08. Statistical significance of all paths was evaluated at the 0.05 alpha level. Direct, indirect, and total effects of teachers' psycho-demographic variables on classroom incivility were computed to test the stated hypotheses. Decisions on hypotheses were made based on the significance and direction of these effects, as well as the overall model fit.

9. Results

9.1. Hypothesis One

H₁: Teachers' psycho-demographic variables will not significantly predict classroom incivility among secondary school students.

Table 1. Total Effects of Teachers' Psycho-Demographic Variables on Classroom Incivility

Variable	Total effect (β)	Direction	Significance
Work Experience	-0.73	Negative	Significant
Academic Qualificatio	-0.16	Negative	Significant
Teaching Efficacy	-0.80	Negative	Significant
Communicative Behaviour	-0.95	Negative	Significant
Teacher Credibility	-0.88	Negative	Significant
Personality	-0.71	Negative	Significant
Classroom Management	-0.69	Negative	Significant
Emotional Intelligence	-0.66	Negative	Significant
Gender	+0.14	Positive	Not Significant

Table 1 shows the total effects of teachers psycho-demographic variables on classroom incivility. The structural equation modelling revealed that teachers' psycho-demographic variables significantly predicted classroom incivility among secondary school students. Eight of the nine teacher variables examined demonstrated statistically significant negative total effects on classroom incivility, indicating that improvements in these variables were associated with reductions in uncivil classroom behaviours. Teachers' gender, however, showed a positive but non-significant effect. Therefore, the hypothesis was rejected.

9.2. Hypothesis Two

H₂: There will be no significant direct or indirect effects of teachers' psycho-demographic variables on classroom incivility.

Table 2. Direct, Indirect, and Total Effects of Teachers' Variables on Classroom Incivility

Variable	Direct Effect	Indirect Effect	Total Effect
Communicative Behaviour	-0.41	-0.54	-0.95
Teacher Credibility	-0.33	-0.55	-0.88
Teaching Efficacy	0.05	0.75	0.80
Emotional Intelligence	-0.06	-0.60	-0.66
Classroom Management	-0.01	-0.68	-0.69
Personality	0.16	-0.87	-0.71

Table 2 shows the direct, indirect and total effects of teachers' psycho-demographic variables on classroom incivility. Results indicated the presence of both direct and indirect causal effects. Communicative behaviour, credibility, work experience, and academic qualification exerted direct negative effects on classroom incivility. Teaching efficacy, emotional intelligence, personality, and classroom management exerted indirect effects, primarily mediated through communicative behaviour and teacher credibility. Approximately 47.7 % of the total causal effects were direct, while 52.3 % occurred indirectly, confirming the existence of a complex mediated causal structure. Therefore, the hypothesis that there will be no significant direct or indirect effects of teachers' psycho-demographic variables on classroom incivility was rejected

9.3. Hypothesis Three

H₃: The hypothesised path model will not significantly fit the data.

Table 3. Model Fit Summary of the Hypothesised and the Validated Model

Fit indices	Recommended level	Hypothesised Model	Validated Model	Remark
Goodness-of-fit				
χ^2	≥ 1	5730.721	65.791	Fit
Df	≥ 1	45	23	Fit
P	$\geq .05$	0.000	0.050	Fit
CMIN/df		127.35	2.860	Fit
Incremental				
NFI	$\geq .95$	0.000	0.989	Fit
TLI	$\geq .95$	0.000	0.985	Fit
CFI	$\geq .95$	0.000	0.992	Fit
Absolute				
GFI	$> .90$	0.229	0.971	Fit
AGFI	≈ 1.00	0.057	0.931	Fit
RMSEA	$\leq .06$	0.535	0.065	Fit

Key: χ^2 = Chi-square; df = Degree of freedom; P= Probability level; CMIN/Df= Minimum discrepancy per degree of freedom; NFI= Normed fit index; TLI= Tucker-Lewis index; CFI= Comparative fit index; GFI= Goodness-of-fit; AGFI= Adjusted Goodness-of-fit; RMSEA= Root mean square error of approximation.

A thorough comparison of the fit indices of the proposed and verified models is shown in Table 4.4, which evaluates goodness-of-fit, incremental fit, and absolute fit. The chi-square (χ^2) goodness-of-fit score for the hypothesised and verified models was 5730.721, indicating a fit to the data. Nonetheless, both models showed values larger than or equal to 1 when degrees of freedom (df) were taken into account; the verified model had a Df of 23 and the hypothesised model had 45, suggesting a suitable match. Additionally, both models' corresponding p-values were 0.000, suggesting a lack of fit. However, CMIN/df, the ratio of χ^2 to df, showed values of 2.860 for the validated model and 127.35 for the hypothesised model, indicating good fits for both.

The Normed Fit Index (NFI), Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI), and Comparative Fit Index (CFI), which measure incremental fit, showed values of 0.000 for the hypothesised model and values at or above 0.95 for the validated model, suggesting that both models fit well. In terms of absolute fit indices, the validated model's Goodness-of-Fit Index (GFI) and Adjusted Goodness-of-Fit Index (AGFI) both reached the suggested values ($>.90$), however the hypothesised model did not. Furthermore, for the hypothesised model, the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) was higher than the suggested threshold ($\leq.06$), while for the verified model, it was within an acceptable range. All things considered, these comparisons indicate that the verified model fits the data better across a range of fit indices, even though the proposed model may need to be improved. Only 21 of the 44 routes in the proposed model were significant and resulted in a model that could illustrate the causal relationships between the independent variables and secondary school students' rudeness in the classroom. Overall, the revalidated model shows that the structural equation for causal effects on secondary school students' classroom incivility was better explained by a combination of work experience (PZt.2), academic background (PZt.3), and particular facets of teachers' credibility and communication. The hypothesised model was refined by deleting non-significant paths. Since the resulting validated model demonstrated improved goodness-of-fit indices and greater explanatory power, therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

9.4. Path Diagram of the Validated Model

Figure 1. Validated Path Model of Teachers' Psycho-Demographic Variables and Classroom Incivility

10. Discussion

The findings of this study revealed that teachers' psycho-demographic variables significantly predicted classroom incivility among secondary school students in Ogun State, Nigeria. The rejection of Hypothesis One implies that

variables such as communicative behaviour, teacher credibility, teaching efficacy, emotional intelligence, personality, classroom management, work experience, and academic qualification contribute significantly to reducing uncivil classroom behaviours. This finding supports the assumptions of Social Exchange Theory advanced by George Homans (1958), which explains that students tend to reciprocate positive teacher behaviours with cooperation and civility. The finding is consistent with the study of Adewale et al. (2025), who reported that teachers' communication patterns significantly influence the management of disruptive classroom behaviours among secondary school students. The finding also agrees with García et al. (2023), who found that teacher credibility enhances students' motivation, respect, and compliance in classroom settings. In the same vein, Agokei (2021) established that emotionally intelligent teachers are more effective in maintaining classroom discipline and resolving behavioural conflicts. The implication of these findings is that teachers who demonstrate competence, emotional responsiveness, and effective communication are more likely to create orderly and supportive classroom environments that discourage incivility.

The findings further revealed that teachers' psycho-demographic variables exerted both direct and indirect effects on classroom incivility, this leads to the rejection of Hypothesis Two. Specifically, communicative behaviour and teacher credibility exerted strong direct effects on classroom incivility, while teaching efficacy, emotional intelligence, personality, and classroom management demonstrated substantial indirect effects mediated through communication and credibility. This finding corroborates Adeyemo and Agokei (2014), who found that emotional intelligence and teacher efficacy significantly predict effective classroom management. The finding also supports Agokei (2021), who reported that emotional intelligence contributes indirectly to classroom control through improved interpersonal relationships and behavioural regulation. Furthermore, the finding aligns with McCroskey and Teven (1999), who asserted that teachers perceived as competent, trustworthy, and caring are more likely to gain students' cooperation and compliance. The result therefore suggests that classroom incivility is strongly shaped by teachers' interpersonal and psychological characteristics rather than by student factors alone.

The findings also showed that the validated path model demonstrated a better goodness-of-fit than the hypothesised model, indicating that classroom incivility is better explained through a multivariate causal framework involving interconnected teacher variables. The elimination of non-significant paths improved the explanatory strength and parsimony of the model. The non-significant influence of gender found in this study supports the submission of Adewale et al. (2025), who reported that communication competence is more influential in classroom management than demographic variables such as gender. In addition, the dominant influence of communicative behaviour and teacher credibility corroborates García et al. (2023), who identified teacher credibility as a major determinant of students' classroom attitudes and behavioural compliance. Collectively, the findings indicate that classroom incivility is fundamentally a teacher-mediated phenomenon shaped by communication effectiveness, emotional intelligence, credibility, and instructional

competence. Effective classroom control therefore depends largely on positive teacher–student interactions and psychologically supportive classroom practices.

REFERENCES

1. Adewale, S., Tahir M. B, Ashiru, I. O & Sanni, M. O. (2025). The Role of Teachers' Communication and Gender in Managing Students' Disruptive Behaviours in Secondary Schools. *Educational Perspectives*, 13(2), 7-15.
2. Agokei, R. C. (2021). Emotional intelligence and classroom management effectiveness among teachers. *African Journal of Educational Studies*, 12(1), 78–92.
3. Ani Cahyadi, Hendryadi, H. and Agoestina Mappadang. (2021). Workplace and Classroom Incivility and Learning Engagement: The Moderating Role of Locus of Control. *International Journal for Educational Integrity*, 17(4) <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40979-021-00071-z>
4. Chirag, D. P. (2020). Classroom Incivility Observed by Faculty and Students of Management Education. *IOSR Journal of Humanities And Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*, 25(12), Series 10 (December. 2020), 32-40, e-ISSN: 2279-0837, p-ISSN: 2279-0845. www.iosrjournals.org
5. García, A. J., Froment, F. A. & Bohórquez, M. R. (2023). University Teacher Credibility as a Strategy to Motivate Students. *Journal of New Approaches in Educational Research*, 12(2), 292-306. DOI: 10.7821/naer.2023.7.1469
6. Gosling, S. D., Rentfrow, P. J., & Swann, W. B. (2003). A very brief measure of the Big-Five personality domains. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 37(6), 504–528.
7. Homans, G. C. (1958). Social behavior as exchange. *American Journal of Sociology*, 63(6), 597–606.
8. Law, K. S., Wong, C. S., & Song, L. J. (2002). The construct and criterion validity of emotional intelligence. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 87(3), 483–496.
9. McCroskey, J. C., & Teven, J. J. (1999). Goodwill: A reexamination of the construct. *Communication Monographs*, 66(1), 90–103.
10. McKinne, E. (2008). Classroom incivility scale development and validation. *Educational Research Quarterly*, 31(3), 34–45.
11. Natalie Spadafora, Elizabeth A, Naomi C. Z. A, |Anthony A. V. (2025). Modeling Changes in Classroom Incivility Across Adolescence. *Journal of Adolescence*, 97, 1680–1686. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jad.12509>
12. Ogunwole, E. A. (2020). Effects of Behavioural Modification Techniques on Disruptive Communication Behaviour among Secondary Students in Zaria Metropolis of Kaduna State, Nigeria. *Prestige Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 3(2).
13. Pianta, R. C. (1999). *Enhancing relationships between children and teachers*. Washington, DC: American Psychological Association.
14. Qiyu, B., Yuhan, Z., Qi, D., Tomoko, K. (2024). Understanding school incivility: Exploring its impact on students and practical interventions.

Computers in Human Behavior, 152, March 2024, 10803.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2023.10803>

15. Tschannen-Moran, M., & Hoy, A. W. (2001). Teacher efficacy: Capturing an elusive construct. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 17(7), 783–805.
16. Yeliz, K. (2016). Classroom management scale development. *Educational Sciences Journal*, 11(2), 123–138.